

AGRI MAGAZINE

(International E-Magazine for Agricultural Articles)

Volume: 02, Issue: 05 (May, 2025)

Available online at <http://www.agrimagazine.in>

© Agri Magazine, ISSN: 3048-8656

Biotech Interventions of an Endangered Medicinal Plant

Withania coagulans

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Withania coagulans (Family: Solanaceae) is widely distributed in North-West India; its Sanskrit name is Rishyagandha, its English name is Indian Rennet or Vegetable Rennet, and its trade name is Panir Bed. It's also found in Pakistan and Afghanistan. The plant is a perennial shrub and grows in the Eastern Mediterranean and further in South Asia. The plant is referred to as 'Akri' or 'Puni-ke-bij' in Hindi, Spicebajja in Afghan, Khamjira in Punjabi, while in Sindhi it is called Punir band or Punirja-fota' (Vaibhav *et al.*, 2013). Jain *et al.* (2009) claimed it to be a critically endangered medicinal herb from the Indian arid region. The fruits in Punjab are utilised for the preparation of coagulating enzyme used for milk curdling, which is 'paneer' and hence is also called "Doda Paneer". They are employed in treating dyspepsia, flatulent colic, and other bowel disorders. In some areas of the Pak-Indian subcontinent, the berries serve as a blood detoxifier. The twigs are used for chewing as a teeth cleaner and the plant's smoke is used to relieve toothache (Gupta *et al.*, 2012). It is indicated for nervous exhaustion, disability, mental, insomnia, wasting disease, failure to thrive in children, impotence and so forth. The fruit is indicated for liver problems, asthma and biliousness and flowers for diabetes (Mathur and Agrawal, 2011). Administration of aqueous extract of fruits of *Withania coagulans* Dunal significantly controls the blood sugar, serum cholesterol, serum LPO, and hepatic LPO levels at the highest concentration of 1 g/kg, po in streptozotocin.

W. coagulans has been included in diverse medicinal products, which has led to the species being endangered because permanent stocks have been overexploited. Excessive natural harvesting, ineffective cultivation strategies, self-incompatibility, and a restricted seed environment, in conjunction with the polygamous character of the flowers, contribute to an alarming risk of extinction (Gilani *et al.*, 2009).

Botanical Description and Distribution

Withania coagulans is recognized by various vernacular names across different regions, reflecting its widespread traditional use and cultural significance. In Bengal, it is commonly known as Asvagandha, while in Bombay, it is referred to as Kaknaj. In Gwalior, the plant goes by the name Asgandha, and in Punjab, it is locally called Khamjaria, Khamjira, or Panir. In Arabic, it is known by the names Javzulmizaja and Kaknajehindi. These diverse regional names underscore the ethnobotanical relevance of *Withania coagulans* in various traditional medicinal systems. (Gupta *et al.*, 2013)

The plant has lanceolate-oblong leaves (2.5-7.5 cm long and 1.5 cm broad) and yellowish, dioecious, polygamous flowers (0.7-1.2 cm across) in axillary cymose racemes

(Gupta *et al.*, 2012). Male and female flowers form separate clusters. Male flowers possess glabrous filaments and larger anthers, while female flowers have shorter filaments and sterile anthers. The ovoid ovary has smooth style and glabrous head like stigma. Fruits consist of a scurfy calyx that contains a granule like structure which is 6-8mm in diameter. Seeds are rounded and dark glabrous which resemble ears. Natural regeneration with seed occurs and is prevalent until January when fruits become apuricable, usually maturing by May (Kirtikar K.R. and Basu B.D., 1999)

Fig.- Geographical distribution of *W. coagulans* (source: <https://www.gbif.org/species/3801167>, accessed on 16 May 2023).

Ethnobotanical and Pharmacological Importance

Withania coagulans exhibits notable anti-inflammatory activity. Alcoholic and hydroalcoholic extracts have shown significant effects in animal models, such as carrageenan-induced rat paw edema and formalin-induced inflammation (Rajurkar *et al.*, 2001). Active constituents like 3 β -Hydroxy-2,3-dihydrowithanolide F demonstrated strong anti-inflammatory effects but also potential hepatotoxicity. These effects are partially due to COX-2 enzyme inhibition, offering advantages over non-selective NSAIDs. Withanolides showed selective COX-2 inhibition, suggesting potential as alternatives to traditional NSAIDs (Nithya *et al.*, 2010).

In terms of anti-cancer activity, withanolides such as withacoagulin A-E and withanolide F showed cytotoxic and antiproliferative effects against various cancer cell lines (Choudhary *et al.*, 2010). Withaferin A, in particular, inhibited NF- κ B signaling and induced apoptosis in lung and head-neck carcinoma cells (Ichikawa *et al.*, 2006). These compounds may arrest the cell cycle at G2/M phase and downregulate pro-inflammatory and tumor-promoting factors. Additionally, *W. coagulans* and its extracts have shown promise in Alzheimer's disease by modulating amyloid pathways, cholinesterase inhibition, and calcium channel blocking (Patil *et al.*, 2010).

Fig- Uses of *Withania coagulans* (Ahmad *et al.*, 1997)

Conservation Status and Challenges

Withania coagulans, an important medicinal plant native to drier regions of India, Pakistan, and parts of the Middle East, is facing increasing conservation challenges due to overexploitation and habitat degradation. Although not yet formally listed as endangered on the IUCN Red List, several regional studies have classified it as threatened or vulnerable due to unsustainable harvesting practices, mainly for its fruits, roots, and seeds (Kumar *et al.*, 2013). The plant's slow growth, poor seed germination, and limited natural regeneration exacerbate the problem (Sharma & Kumar, 2010).

Habitat destruction due to agricultural expansion, overgrazing, and urbanization also contributes to its declining population in the wild (Kala, 2005). Moreover, lack of awareness and insufficient inclusion of the species in conservation programs hampers its protection. Although some efforts are underway for its in-situ and ex-situ conservation, including micropropagation and cultivation protocols, these are limited in scale (Ahmed *et al.*, 2012). To ensure long-term survival, integrated strategies involving community participation, sustainable harvesting, and conservation education are essential. Promoting commercial cultivation with proper training may also reduce pressure on wild populations and support local livelihoods.

Biotechnological Intervention for the Conservation and Production

The natural populations of *Withania coagulans*, a medicinal plant with significant pharmacological potential, are rapidly declining due to overharvesting, ineffective natural regeneration, and habitat loss (Chapin *et al.*, 2000). The species is now considered severely endangered due to its dry habitat and poor regeneration capabilities (Rathore *et al.*, 2012). Biotechnological approaches offer promising tools for conserving biodiversity and ensuring sustainable utilization of this valuable plant species.

In Vitro Propagation in *Withania coagulans*: *In vitro* propagation methods, especially direct organogenesis using shoot tips, nodes, and axillary buds, help preserve clonal fidelity better than callus-mediated indirect organogenesis, which may lead to genetic instability (Shahzad *et al.*, 2017). A crucial step in micropropagation is the disinfection of explants using agents like sodium hypochlorite, ethanol, Bavistin, and hydrogen peroxide to prevent contamination and ensure healthy culture development.

The culture medium's composition including growth regulators, sucrose, agar, and pH significantly affects the success of micropropagation. Most species thrive in a pH range of 5.5-6.5 (Padmavathy *et al.*, 2021). Sucrose acts as a primary carbon source and osmotic agent, while also influencing gene expression and development. Agar concentrations typically range from 0.8-1.0% (w/v) and provide physical support, though higher concentrations may inhibit rooting (Zhou *et al.*, 2020).

Environmental culture conditions like temperature, photoperiod, and light intensity also play vital roles in tissue growth and plantlet development (Ahmad *et al.*, 2023). Optimizing these parameters is essential for producing robust, viable plantlets.

Synthetic Seed Production: Synthetic seed technology, involving the encapsulation of plant tissue (e.g., nodal and shoot tip explants) using materials like sodium alginate and calcium chloride, presents a practical approach for the propagation and conservation of *W. coagulans* (Sharma, 2013). Encapsulation using 3% sodium alginate and 100 mM CaCl₂·2H₂O showed 96% regeneration on a 0.75% MS medium supplemented with 0.57 μM IAA and 1.11 μM BA (Bhandari, 1990). Plantlets derived from synthetic seeds exhibited 72% revival after storage at 4°C for 60 days and successfully acclimatized under natural conditions.

Economic and Environmental Sustainability

Withania coagulans, commonly known as Indian Rennet, holds significant promise for both economic and environmental sustainability. Economically, its high demand in the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries for withanolide-based compounds positions it as a valuable cash crop. Withanolides exhibit antitumor, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties, making *W. coagulans* a potential source of income for rural

and tribal communities involved in its cultivation and trade (Gilani *et al.*, 2009). Sustainable harvesting practices and value addition through biotechnological interventions can enhance income generation while conserving biodiversity.

Environmentally, the species plays a role in stabilizing arid and semi-arid ecosystems, where it naturally grows. Its drought-resistant nature makes it suitable for afforestation in degraded lands and water-scarce areas, contributing to ecological restoration (Rathore *et al.*, 2012). Biotechnological approaches like micropropagation and synthetic seed technology ensure conservation and mass propagation without overexploiting wild populations (Sharma, 2013). This sustainable production model not only preserves the plant's genetic diversity but also reduces pressure on natural habitats, aligning with long-term conservation goals.

Conclusion

Withania coagulans is of importance, sustainably and medicinally, due to its hypolipidemic effects. The plant is also known for having anti-cancer properties alongside hypoglycemic and neuroprotective effects that aid in traditional and modern medicinal systems. These medicinal plants are located in arid zones in India, Pakistan, and parts of the Middle East. However, the population is placed at high risk due to the poor natural regeneration. Efforts in conservation and recovering the populations of sustainable *Withania coagulans* is essential in sophisticated and expanding forms. Strategies involving both in situ and ex-situ conservation measures are necessary. Large-scale micropropagation and synthetic seed technology provide great means to preserve the plant. Applying those, along with sustainable farming methods, can slow the dependency on wild populations of the plant. By integrating economic benefits with conservation-focused strategies, *W. coagulans* serves as a model for balancing commercial utility and ecological responsibility. In addition, raising awareness and adjusting policies that support investment towards directed *W. coagulans* can slow down dependency on the wild while greatly aiding surrounding communities economically. Finally, the inclusion of biotechnology with traditional knowledge makes the unsupported scientific exercise of tasking *Withania coagulans* easier job simplified.

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